

On geometric properties of generalized concave meromorphic functions

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Abstract: In this work, we introduce a generalized class of concave meromorphic functions denoted as $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$ defined by Salagean differential operator \mathcal{D}^n , which is an operator defined on the concave meromorphic function $g(z)$, $\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{D}^{n-1} g(z))$, $\{n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$, and study some of the properties namely; inclusion, integral representation, closure under an integral operator, sufficient condition, coefficient inequality, growth and distortion of this class.

Key words: Salagean operator, concave and meromorphic functions

1. Introduction

Let g be define as

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k. \tag{1}$$

meromorphic function with a simple pole at the origin, the unit disk be denoted by $\{U = |z| < 1\}$ and concave domain which is the exterior of a closed convex domain be denoted by \mathbb{E} . We say the function g of the form (1), is concave if it maps the U to \mathbb{E} , denoted by \mathcal{K}_0 satisfying the following inequality as define below:

Definition 1.1. [16] The function $g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k$ belong to the class \mathcal{K}_o if it satisfies the inequality

$$Re \left(1 + z \frac{g''(z)}{g'(z)} \right) < 0, z \in U. \tag{2}$$

For more details of concave univalent functions and the types, (see $\{[1],[2],[3],[4],[6],[7] [19]\}$).

The integral representation of the functions in the class \mathcal{K}_0 was first considered in [15, 16] as stated below:

Theorem 1.1. [15] The function $g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k$ belong to the class function \mathcal{K}_o if and only if there exists a positive measure $\mu(t)$ and $\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} d\mu(t) = 1$ and $\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{-it} d\mu(t) = 0$, such that for $z \in U$.

$$g'(z) = -\frac{1}{z} \exp \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} 2 \log(1 - e^{it} z) d\mu(t). \tag{3}$$

Theorem 1.2. [16] *The function $g = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k$ belong to the class \mathcal{K}_o if there exists a function*

$$\varphi : \mathbb{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}, \text{ with } \varphi(0) = 0 \tag{4}$$

holomorphic in \mathbb{U} , such that for $z \in \mathbb{U}$

$$g'(z) = -\frac{1}{z} \exp \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} 2 \log(1 - e^{it} z) d\mu(t). \tag{5}$$

Conversely, for any holomorphic function $\varphi : \mathbb{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$, with $\varphi(0) = 0$, there exists a function $g \in \mathcal{K}_o$.

In [13, 14, 16], the inequality (2) was shown to be the necessary and sufficient condition of the concave meromorphic function of the form (1) and also deduced the coefficient inequality

$$|a_1|^2 + 3|a_2| \leq 1 \tag{6}$$

by applying an invariant form of Schwarz’s lemma involving with Schwarzian derivative and in [4], Al-Kaseasbeh, estimated a_k for $k = 2, 3, \dots$ for the function $g(z)$ satisfying inequality (2).

Using the Salagean differential operator denoted as \mathcal{D}^n is defined as $\mathcal{D}^0 g(z) = g(z)$, $\mathcal{D}^1 g(z) = z g'(z)$, $\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = D(\mathcal{D}^{n-1} g(z))$, $\{n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$ and its integral operator define as $\mathcal{I}^0 g(z) = g(z)$, $\mathcal{I}^1 g(z) = \int_0^z \frac{g(t)}{t} dt$, $\mathcal{I}^n g(z) = \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{I}^{n-1} g(z))$, $\{n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$, both appeared in [17].

The new generalized class of concave meromorphic functions is define as follows:

Definition 1.2. The function $g : \mathbb{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}$, $g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k$ belong to the class of concave meromorphic univalent function of order ζ , denoted as $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \zeta < 1$, if and only if it satisfies the inequality

$$Re \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) < -\zeta, z \in \mathbb{U}. \tag{7}$$

Similarly, the class $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$ can be written as

$$-Re \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > \zeta, z \in \mathbb{U}. \tag{8}$$

Our focus in this work is to study the concave meromorphic function using the Salagean derivative denoted by $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$ and establish some of it geometric properties.

2. Preliminary Lemmas

Lemma 2.1. [5] *Let \mathcal{P} be holomorphic in \mathbb{U} with $\mathcal{P}(0) = 1$ and suppose that*

$$Re \left(\frac{z \mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \right) > \frac{3\zeta - 1}{2\zeta}, \in \mathbb{U}.$$

Then $Re \mathcal{P}(z) > 2^{1-1/\zeta}$, $1/2 \leq \zeta < 1$, $z \in \mathbb{U}$ and the constant $2^{1-1/\zeta}$ is the best possible.

Lemma 2.2. [9, 11] Let $\mathcal{P}(z)$ be analytic in \mathbb{U} , $\mathcal{P}(0) = 1$ and suppose that

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \mathcal{P}(z) - \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \right\} > \zeta, (z \in \mathbb{U}, 0 \leq \zeta < 1).$$

Then $\operatorname{Re}\mathcal{P}(z) > \zeta$ in \mathbb{U} .

Lemma 2.3. [10] Let $\mathcal{P}(z) = 1 + c_1z + c_2z^2 + \dots$, be analytic in \mathbb{U} and $\{\zeta : 0 \leq \zeta < 1\}$ be a positive real number. Suppose that $\{r : 0 < r < 1\}$, such that

$$\min_{|z| \leq r} \operatorname{Re}\{\mathcal{P}(z)\} = \min_{|z| \leq r} |\mathcal{P}(z)|. \quad (9)$$

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} > \zeta - 1, z \in \mathbb{U}, \quad (10)$$

for $0 < \zeta \leq 1/2$,

and

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} > \zeta/2 - 1, z \in U. \quad (11)$$

for $1/2 < \zeta < 1$,

Then

$$\operatorname{Re}\{\mathcal{P}(z)\} > \zeta, z \in U. \quad (12)$$

Lemma 2.4. [18] Let $\mathcal{P}(z)$ be regular and satisfy $\operatorname{Re}\mathcal{P}(z) > \zeta$, $0 \leq \zeta < 1$ in $|z| < 1$ and let $\mathcal{P}(0) = 1$. Then we have

$$\mathcal{P}(z) = \frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)z\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)} \quad (13)$$

where $\phi(z)$ is any regular function in $|z| < 1$, satisfying $|\phi(z)| < 1$ in $|z| < 1$ and any function $\mathcal{P}(z)$ given by the above formula is regular and satisfies $\operatorname{Re}\mathcal{P}(z) > \zeta$ in $|z| < 1$.

Lemma 2.5. [8, 15] Let $w(z)$ be non-constant regular in $\{z : |z| < 1\}$ $w(0) = 0$. If $w(z)$ attains its maximum value on the circle $|z| = r < 1$ at z_0 , we have $z_0w'(z_0) = kw(z_0)$, where k is a real number, $k \geq 1$.

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \zeta < 1$. Then $\mathcal{K}_0^{n+1}(\zeta) \subset \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$.

Proof. The function $g(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, if $\mathcal{P} \in \mathcal{P}(\zeta)$ so that

$$-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \mathcal{P}(z). \quad (14)$$

By differentiating (14), we obtain

$$\frac{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' \mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))^2} - \frac{(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \mathcal{P}'(z) \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' \mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))^2} - \frac{z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = z\mathcal{P}'(z). \quad (16)$$

Divide through by $\mathcal{P}(z)$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} - \frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)}. \quad (17)$$

By the relation $z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)$ and $z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)$, then (17) becomes

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} - \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \quad (18)$$

which implies that

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} = \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} + \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)}. \quad (19)$$

From (19), we have that

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} = -\mathcal{P}(z) + \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \quad (20)$$

$$-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} = \mathcal{P}(z) - \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)}. \quad (21)$$

Since

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \mathcal{P}(z) - \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \right\} > \zeta$$

by Lemma 2.2. Then $-\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > \zeta$ and we have the inclusion. \square

Theorem 3.2. *If $g(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, and satisfies*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)} - \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > \frac{\zeta - 1}{2\zeta}.$$

Then $-\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > 2^{1-1/\zeta}$, $1/2 \leq \zeta < 1$, $z \in \mathbb{U}$.

Proof. The function $g(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, if $\mathcal{P} \in \mathcal{P}(\zeta)$, then

$$-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \mathcal{P}(z). \quad (22)$$

By differentiating (22), we obtain

$$\frac{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' \mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))^2} - \frac{(\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \mathcal{P}'(z) \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' \mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z)}{(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))^2} - \frac{z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1} g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = z\mathcal{P}'(z) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} - \frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)}. \quad (25)$$

By the fact that $z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)$ and $z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)$, then (25) becomes

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} - \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)}. \quad (26)$$

By the condition of the theorem,

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} \right) = \operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} - \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} + 1 \right) > \frac{3\zeta - 1}{2\zeta} \quad (27)$$

which is equivalent to

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} - \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > \frac{\zeta - 1}{2\zeta}. \quad (28)$$

Thus by Lemma 2.1, $\operatorname{Re}\mathcal{P}(z) > 2^{1/\zeta-1}$, $1/2 \leq \zeta < 1$, which concludes the result. \square

Theorem 3.3. *Let $f \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \zeta < 1$. Then*

$$g(z) = \mathcal{I}_n \left\{ \frac{1}{z} \exp \left\{ (2 - 2\zeta) \int_0^z \frac{\phi(t)}{1 + t\phi(t)} dt \right\} \right\}. \quad (29)$$

where $\phi(z)$ is regular in $|z| < 1$ with $|\phi(z)| < 1$.

Proof. Let $g \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, then by Lemma 2.4

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = -\frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)z\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)}. \quad (30)$$

From the relation $z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)$, we obtain

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = -\frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)z\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)}. \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} + 1 = \frac{(2 - 2\zeta)z\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)}. \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} + \frac{1}{z} = \frac{(2 - 2\zeta)\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)}. \quad (33)$$

We can have that

$$\frac{d}{dz} (\log z\mathcal{D}^n g(z)) = \frac{(2 - 2\zeta)\phi(z)}{1 + z\phi(z)}. \quad (34)$$

Which gives

$$\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = \frac{1}{z} \exp \left\{ (2 - 2\zeta) \int_0^z \frac{\phi(t)}{1 + t\phi(t)} dt \right\}. \quad (35)$$

Equation (29) can easily be obtained from (35). \square

Corollary 3.1. . If $n = 1$, then

$$g(z) = \int_0^z \left\{ \frac{1}{s^2} \left\{ \exp \left\{ (2 - 2\zeta) \int_0^s \frac{\phi(t)}{1 + t\phi(t)} dt \right\} \right\} \right\}. \quad (36)$$

Corollary 3.2. [1]. If $n = 1$, $\zeta = 0$, then

$$g(z) = \int_0^z \left\{ \frac{1}{s^2} \left\{ \exp \left\{ \int_0^s \frac{2\phi(t)}{1 + t\phi(t)} dt \right\} \right\} \right\}. \quad (37)$$

Theorem 3.4. Let

$$G(z) = \frac{c}{z^{c+1}} \int_0^z t^c g(t) dt. \quad (38)$$

If $G(z)$ satisfies the condition

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} < \frac{1 - \zeta}{2c + 2 - 2\zeta} - \zeta \quad (39)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $0 \leq \zeta < 1$ and $c > 0$. Then $G(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$.

Proof. Let

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = -\mathcal{P}(z). \quad (40)$$

From (38), we have

$$z^{c+1}G(z) = c \int_0^z t^c g(t) dt \quad (41)$$

$$(c + 1)z^c G(z) + z^{c+1}G'(z) = cz^c g(z) \quad (42)$$

$$(c + 1)G(z) + zG'(z) = cg(z) \quad (43)$$

$$(c + 1)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) + z(\mathcal{D}^n G(z))' = c\mathcal{D}^n g(z) \quad (44)$$

$$(c + 1)\mathcal{D}^{n+1}G(z) + z(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}G(z))' = c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z) \quad (45)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z) = -(c + 1)[\mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z)] - z[\mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z)]' \quad (46)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z) = -(c + 1)[\mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z)] - z\mathcal{P}'(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) - \mathcal{P}(z)z[\mathcal{D}^n G(z)]' \quad (47)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z) = -(c + 1)[\mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z)] - z\mathcal{P}'(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) + \mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^{n+1}G(z) \quad (48)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z) = -[(c + 1)\mathcal{P}(z)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) - z\mathcal{P}'(z) + \mathcal{P}^2(z)]\mathcal{D}^n G(z). \quad (49)$$

Also

$$c\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = (c + 1)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) + z(\mathcal{D}^n G(z))' \quad (50)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = (c + 1)\mathcal{D}^n G(z) + \mathcal{D}^{n+1}G(z) \quad (51)$$

$$c\mathcal{D}^n g(z) = [(c + 1) - \mathcal{P}(z)]\mathcal{D}^n G(z) \quad (52)$$

$$\frac{c\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{c\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{-[(c+1)\mathcal{P}(z) - z\mathcal{P}'(z) + \mathcal{P}^2(z)]\mathcal{D}^n G(z)}{[(c+1) - \mathcal{P}(z)]\mathcal{D}^n G(z)} \quad (53)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \frac{-[(c+1) - \mathcal{P}(z)]\mathcal{P}(z) - z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{[(c+1) - \mathcal{P}(z)]} \quad (54)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = -\mathcal{P}(z) - \frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{[(c+1) - \mathcal{P}(z)]}. \quad (55)$$

From Lemma (2.4), let

$$p(z) = \frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)w(z)}{1 + w(z)} \quad (56)$$

where $w(z) = z\phi(z)$, $w(0) = 0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$,

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = - \left\{ \frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)w(z)}{1 + w(z)} + \frac{(2\zeta - 2)zw'(z)}{(1 + w(z))[c + (2 + c - 2\zeta)]w(z)} \right\}. \quad (57)$$

By Lemma 2.5, there exists $k \geq 1$ such that $z_0 w'(z_0) = kw(z_0)$, we obtain

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = - \left\{ \frac{1 + (2\zeta - 1)w(z_0)}{1 + w(z_0)} + \frac{(2\zeta - 2)kw(z_0)}{(1 + w(z_0))[c + (2 + c - 2\zeta)]w(z_0)} \right\}. \quad (58)$$

So that

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \geq \frac{1 - \zeta}{2c + 2 - 2\zeta} - \zeta > 0, \quad (59)$$

which is a contradiction for $|w(z)| < 1$, then $G(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$. \square

Corollary 3.3. *If $n = 1$, then*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{zg''(z)}{g(z)} \right) < \frac{1 - \zeta}{2c + 2 - 2\zeta} - \zeta. \quad (60)$$

Corollary 3.4. *If $n = 1$, $\zeta = 0$, then*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{zg''(z)}{g(z)} \right) < \frac{1}{2 + 2c}. \quad (61)$$

Corollary 3.5. [12]. *If $n = 1$, $\zeta = 0$ and $c = 1$ then*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{zg''(z)}{g(z)} \right) < \frac{1}{4}. \quad (62)$$

Theorem 3.5. *For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq \zeta < 1$. The class $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, is a convex family of concave meromorphic univalent functions.*

Proof. Let $g(z)$ and $k(z)$ be in the class $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$. For $t \in (0, 1)$, it suffices to show that the function $h(z) = (1-t)g(z) + tk(z)$ is in the class $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$.

$$-Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}h(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n h(z)} = \frac{(1-t)\left[\frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} a_k z^k\right] + t\left[\frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} b_k z^k\right]}{(1-t)\left[\frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n a_k z^k\right] + t\left[\frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n b_k z^k\right]}. \quad (63)$$

$$-Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}h(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n h(z)} = \frac{\frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} [(1-t)a_k + tb_k z^k] z^k}{\frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n [(1-t)a_k + tb_k] z^k}. \quad (64)$$

Since $g(z), k(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$. This implies that $h(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(1-t)a_k + tb_k] z^k \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$. Therefore

$$-Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}h(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n h(z)} > \zeta. \quad (65)$$

□

Theorem 3.6. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $0 \leq \zeta < 1$. Suppose that $g(z)$ satisfies the condition

$$\min_{|z| \leq r} Re \left\{ -\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right\} = \min_{|z| \leq r} \left| -\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right|, \quad (66)$$

for arbitrary $(0 < r < 1)$

$$Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} < Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} - \zeta + 1, \quad (67)$$

for $0 < \zeta \leq 1/2$.

and

$$Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}f(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}f(z)} < Re \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}f(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n f(z)} - \frac{\zeta}{2} + 1, z \in U, \quad (68)$$

for $1/2 < \zeta < 1$.

Then $f(z) \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$.

Proof. Let

$$-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} = \mathcal{P}(z) \quad (69)$$

then

$$\frac{z\mathcal{P}'(z)}{\mathcal{P}(z)} = -\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+2}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)} + \frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \quad (70)$$

By Lemma 2.3, condition (67) and (68), we have that

$$-Re \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) > \zeta. \quad (71)$$

□

Theorem 3.7. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $g(z)$ be of the form (1). For $0 \leq \zeta < 1$, then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n (\zeta + k) |a_k| \leq 1 - \zeta. \quad (72)$$

if and only $f \in \mathcal{K}^n(\zeta)$.

Proof. Suppose that the condition (72) holds for $(0 \leq \zeta < 1)$, it is sufficient to show that $|1 - \zeta + \alpha| \leq |1 + \beta - \alpha|$ where $Re(-\alpha) \geq \zeta$ which implies that

$$\left| 1 - \zeta + \left(-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right| \leq \left| 1 + \zeta - \left(-\frac{\mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right|.$$

From the relation that $z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))' = \mathcal{D}^{n+1}g(z)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| 1 - \zeta + \left(-\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right| \leq \left| 1 + \zeta - \left(-\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right| \\ & \left| 1 - \zeta + \left(-\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right| - \left| 1 + \zeta - \left(-\frac{z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z))'}{\mathcal{D}^n g(z)} \right) \right| \leq 0 \\ & \left| (1 - \zeta)\mathcal{D}^n g(z) + (-z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z)))' \right| - \left| (1 + \zeta)\mathcal{D}^n g(z) - (-z(\mathcal{D}^n g(z)))' \right| \leq 0 \\ & = \left| (1 - \zeta) \left(\frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n a_k z^k \right) + \frac{(-1)^n}{z} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} a_k z^k \right| \\ & - \left| (1 + \zeta) \left(\frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^n a_k z^k \right) - \frac{(-1)^n}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} a_k z^k \right| \\ & \leq (2 - \zeta) | -1|^n + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(1 - \zeta)k^n - k^{n+1}] |a_k| |z|^{k+1} - \zeta | -1|^n + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(1 + \zeta)k^n + k^{n+1}] |a_k| |z|^{k+1} \\ & = 2[(1 - \zeta) - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (k^n(\zeta + k))] |a_k| \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

From the last inequality, we obtain the condition (72) of the theorem. □

Corollary 3.6. Let $g \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, then

$$|a_k| \leq \frac{1 - \zeta}{k^n(\zeta + k)}, k \geq 1. \quad (73)$$

Equality is obtained for

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - \zeta}{k^n(\zeta + k)}. \quad (74)$$

Theorem 3.8. *Let the function of the form (1) be in $\mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, then for $0 < |z| = r < 1$,*

$$\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r \leq |f(z)| \leq \frac{1}{r} + \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r \quad (75)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{k(1-\zeta)}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r^{k-1} \leq |f'(z)| \leq \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{k(1-\zeta)}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r^{k-1}. \quad (76)$$

Equality in (75) and (76) are obtained for the function

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}. \quad (77)$$

Proof. Since $f \in \mathcal{K}_0^n(\zeta)$, then from (72), we have that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |a_k| \leq \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}. \quad (78)$$

For $0 < |z| = r < 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} |f(z)| &\leq \left| \frac{1}{z} \right| + \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} + r \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |a_k| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} + \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |f(z)| &\geq \left| \frac{1}{z} \right| - \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k z^k \right| \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r} - r \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |a_k| \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r} - \frac{1-\zeta}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} |f'(z)| &\leq \frac{1}{|z|^2} + \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k a_k z^{k-1} \right| \\ |f'(z)| &\leq \frac{1}{r^2} + r^{k-1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k |a_k| \\ |f'(z)| &\leq \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{k(1-\zeta)}{k^n(\zeta+k)}r^{k-1} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$|f'(z)| \geq \frac{1}{|z|^2} - \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k a_k z^{k-1} \right|$$

$$|f'(z)| \geq \frac{1}{r^2} - r^{k-1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k |a_k|$$

$$|f'(z)| \geq \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{k(1-\zeta)}{k^n(\zeta+k)} r^{k-1}.$$

□

4. Conclusion

In this work we determine the properties which includes inclusion, integral representation, closure under an integral operator, sufficient condition, coefficient inequality, growth and distortion.

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